

GeoApi and Hazmapper: A RESTful API and Responsive User Interface For Geospatial Data In The Natural Hazards Community

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ABSTRACT

The DesignSafe [1] portal is a web-based application created to facilitate researchers in the natural hazards community, providing data storage, computational resources, and publication pipelines to its users. With partners such as the RAPID response field reconnaissance teams who collect data immediately after a disaster event, the geospatial component of the data is essential information needed in subsequent analysis. Storing, searching, and visualizing this geospatial information has subsequently become a need for the DesignSafe and natural hazards community. A typical field reconnaissance mission can generate many gigabytes of geotagged images, videos and point cloud datasets. To integrate these data with the DesignSafe platform, we have developed a new set of RESTful APIs and a single page application to store, query and visualize these datasets.

As one of the requirements for these tools is tight integration with the existing DesignSafe platform, which is built using Tapis [2] APIs, we have implemented the GeoAPI as a separate microservice in the Tapis v2 platform. This design allows us to easily utilize the existing data storage and user management tools built into DesignSafe. Users can access their existing data that is shared with their colleagues and already stored on the DesignSafe platform. Similarly, by utilizing the

authentication services in Tapis, users can access these services with a single account.

The backend has been developed using Python and the Flask framework. Application data is stored in a Postgres database with the PostGIS extension providing geospatial indexing. We have leveraged open-source libraries in the application such as GDAL, PDAL, Laspy, GeoPandas, and Shapely. Reconnaissance teams often use Lidar to collect point cloud data of structures damaged during a natural hazard event. These datasets alone can grow to many hundreds of GB and require additional processing. We use Celery to asynchronously process these data with Potree [3] to visualize them in the browser. Static assets such as images and videos are saved into a Ceph filesystem and are served directly by a Nginx proxy for performance. Maps can be automatically generated from data already in DesignSafe and asynchronously updated when new data is added to the storage system. The application is deployed into a Kubernetes cluster at TACC. A general architecture diagram is shown in figure 1.

To visualize these datasets, we have created Hazmapper 2.0, a single page web application. This application was written in TypeScript using the Angular framework and Leaflet libraries. Additionally, we use an auto generated client library Ng-Tapis [4] to interact with the Tapis APIs. By doing so, we can utilize the API directly from the browser without the need for a separate backend application. External map tiles can be imported through a

searchable interface using QuickMapServices (QMS) APIs [5].

The decoupled backend architecture allows us to have multiple user interfaces that are specialized for different end-user needs. One such example is the Taggit [6] application from Designsafe researchers. Separate from Hazmapper, this application allows for tagging and classification of georeferenced images.

Figure 1.

Keywords—*geospatial; user interface; point clouds; DesignSafe, Tapis*

REFERENCES

[1] Rathje, E., Dawson, C. Padgett, J.E., Pinelli, J.-P., Stanzione, D., Adair, A., Arduino, P., Brandenburg, S.J., Cockerill, T., Dey, C., Esteva, M., Haan, Jr., F.L., Hanlon, M., Kareem, A., Lowes, L., Mock, S., and Mosqueda, G. 2017. “DesignSafe: A New Cyberinfrastructure for Natural Hazards Engineering,” ASCE Natural Hazards Review, doi:10.1061/(ASCE)NH.1527-6996.0000246.
 [2] Tapis <https://tapis-project.org/>
 [3] Potree <https://github.com/potree/potree>
 [4] NgTapis <https://github.com/TACC-Cloud/ng-tapis>
 [5] QuickMapServices <https://qms.nextgis.com/>
 [6] Taggit <https://github.com/taggit-tacc>